

**NUMERICAL STUDY OF MULTI-DIMENSIONAL MULTI-PHASE
FLOW IN THE VACUUM ASSISTED RESIN INFUSION**

Yubo Zhou¹, Min Li¹, Shaokai Wang¹, Yizhuo Gu¹, Yanxia Li¹, Yiquan Li², Shanghong Huang² and
Zuoguang Zhang¹

¹ School of Materials Science and Engineering, Key Laboratory of Aerospace Materials and Performance (Ministry of Education), Beihang University, leemy@buaa.edu.cn, www.buaa.edu.cn

² Beijing Composite Materials Co., Ltd, liyiquan954@sina.com, www.sinoma-composite.cn

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ABSTRACT

Vacuum Assisted Resin Infusion (VARI) has been widely used in manufacturing large-size structures. However, the multi-dimensional flow nearby inlets may cause serious defects in the parts due to unreasonable arrangement of the tooling materials. Also, the air entrainment in the infusing resin affects the process quality. In this paper, a 3-D flow field was simulated by considering the omega flow line, resin distribution mesh, caul plate, porous membrane, peel ply and the preform. The resin system in the flow field was treated as a mixture with three phases: resin, air trapped in resin and residual air in preform. The extra resin distribution mesh between the omega flow line and caul plate was proved to result in a negative effect on the entirely infiltration of resin near inlets. Using the materials with lower permeability could improve the defects around the omega flow line. The higher permeability of the release fabrics and porous membranes might be helpful to accelerate the resin infusion, but it was harmful to improve the qualities of final parts. Using the release materials with lower permeability and deserting the irrational resin distribution mesh simultaneously could lead to the defect-free parts.

1 INTRODUCTION

Among the several manufacturing technologies of Liquid Composite Molding (LCM), Vacuum Assisted Resin Infusion (VARI), which has been developed over the last decade, has clear advantages over the traditional Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) process since it eliminates the costs of the complex and expensive molds required to withstand the injection pressure. Owing to the auxiliary of resin distribution media, the infiltration of resin takes place simultaneously in the preform plane and through the thickness [1]. This technique significantly reduces the filling time of large components as the thickness is much smaller than the in-plane dimensions, but it also complicates the simulation of the infiltration process. Hereby VARI was widely applied in manufacturing large-size productions to fabricating affordable composite parts, such as wind-power blades, boat hulls etc.

Massive efforts had been taken in the experimental and numerical study of the process in VARI. In order to develop more accurate simulation tools which can eventually lead to virtual processing strategies [2], a detailed understanding of the mechanisms of resin flow at the microscopic [3] and mesoscopic [4] level is required. The resin flow at the microscopic and mesoscopic level were carefully analysed by means of X-ray microtomography during in situ infiltration experiments and by means of digital image correlation separately. During the decades the simulation technologies of VARI were greatly promoted [5, 6]. Based on Darcy's law, many mould filling codes such as LIMS [7], RTM-Worx [8] and PAM-RTM [9, 10] have been developed in order to optimize manufacturing processes.

A typical arrangement of the tooling materials was illustrated as Figure 1 (components in black labels). The resin distribution meshes whose permeability was much higher than preforms and the omega flow lines were adopted to shorten the filling time of the resin.

Figure 1: The typical arrangement of the tooling materials in VARI.

However, indentation flaws would be conducted under the omega flow lines with the vacuum pressure applied during manufacturing. When parts require both side flatness, caul plates were placed under the pipes, which were GFRPs with grooves and allowed the resin getting through.

Meanwhile, the flow channels of resin were obviously decreased, while the nonuniform flow fields would affect the penetrations in the preform. Herein extra resin distribution meshes were added between the omega flow line and the caul plate which was illustrated as components in Figure 1 with red labels, hoping the velocity and the uniformity of resin could be improved.

Nevertheless, dry spots under omega flow lines appeared when arrangement of the tooling materials as Figure 1 was applied to manufacture the composite part in the Figure 2, which obviously affected the quality of the final product.

Figure 2: Defects under omega flow line in the part.

Traditionally, defects appeared around the inlet (Figure 2, dry spot under omega flow lines in red frames) that resulted from unreasonable arrangement of the tooling materials cannot be predicted. Because the multi-dimensional flow nearby the inlet was simplified when whole fluid domain was studied, the structures under the inlet were too tiny to be modeled in the full fluid zone. At the same time, the resin system penetrated in the distribution media and preforms was treated as pure resin even though air bubbles trapped in resins were inevitable.

In this paper, a novel attempt was introduced to describe the multi-dimensional and multi-phase flow in the vacuum assisted resin infusion. The numerical study was conducted by considering the omega flow line, caul plate, resin distribution mesh, porous membrane, peel ply and reinforcement and treating the liquid as the mixture of resin, air trapped in resin and residual air in the zone. The defeats nearby the inlet and omega flow line were reappeared in the simulation.

2 MODELLING AND SIMULATION

2.1 Structure of Fluids

As in Figure 3(A), a 3-D flow field was established with the omega flow line, resin distribution mesh, caul plate, porous membrane, peel ply and preform. Owing to the small curvature of the part in Figure 2, the preform in fluid domain could be modeled as a plate. A quarter zone of the flow field was modeled because of the symmetry.

Figure 3: Structures of flow fields.(A: The quarter structures adopted; B: The caul plate with grooves)

The flow fields were created in actual size. The preform, peel ply, porous membrane and resin distribution mesh (A) whose thickness were 4mm, 0.1mm, 0.1mm and 2mm separately shared the same length and width of 200 mm \times 200 mm. In the layer of the caul plate which showed as Figure 3(B), only the flow channels whose size were 50 mm \times 5 mm \times 1 mm were considered. The space between two adjacent caul plate channels was 15 mm, and six caul plate channels were included in fluid zone. The size of the resin distribution mesh (B) between the omega flow line and caul plate was 100 mm \times 100 mm \times 1 mm. The diameter of the omega flow line was 20 mm, whose outline size was 80 mm \times 10 mm \times 40 mm.

The Structure mesh was employed to discrete the 3-D model as Figures 4 (The resin distribution mesh (B) was hid).

Figure 4: The local zoom view of structure meshes around the inlet.

2.2 Simulation Configurations

In the fluid domain, the omega flow line and caul plate were non-porous fluid domain, while the resin distribution mesh, porous membrane, peel ply and preform were modeled as porous media with different permeabilities which complied with the Darcy's law. Meanwhile the fluid was the mixture with three phases: resin, air trapped in resin and residual air in the zone.

The equation for conservation of mass, or continuity equation, could be written as:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla(\rho \vec{v}) = 0 \quad (1)$$

where ρ was the density, t was the time, and v was the velocity.

Conservation of momentum is described by:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho \vec{v}) + \nabla(\rho \vec{v} \vec{v}) = -\nabla p + \nabla \bar{\tau} + \bar{S} \quad (2)$$

where p was the static pressure, $\bar{\tau}$ was the stress tensor, \bar{S} was the source terms came from porous-media. The effect of the gravity was neglected here.

The Volume of Fluid (VOF) model was adopted to describe the behaviours of the mixture of resin, air trapped in resin and residual air in the zone. The q^{th} phase of the VOF model followed the volume fraction equation as:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \alpha_q \rho_q + \nabla(\alpha_q \rho_q \vec{v}_q) = 0 \quad (3)$$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 The effect of the extra resin distribution mesh on the velocity

Steady simulations that the fluid zone was filled by pure resins were conducted. In these attempts, a 0.1 MPa pressure was exerted to the inlet and the pressure of outlet was set as 0. The flow velocity through the thickness at the symmetry of models was illustrated as Figure 5. The negative values of velocity meant that the resin flowed from the vacuum bag to the rigid mold.

Figure 5: The flow velocity of through the thickness at the symmetry of models. (A: with extra resin distribution mesh; B: without extra resin distribution mesh)

Compared to the flow domain without the resin distribution mesh(B), the flow distributions in the fluid zone were obviously changed because of the existence of the extra resin distribution mesh. A noteworthy high-speed area arose at the boundary of the resin distribution mesh(B), which meant a second flow channel might result in negative effects existed in the penetrating process.

3.2 The effect of the extra resin distribution mesh on the dry spot near the inlet

Transient analyses that simulated the true situation were conducted to study the effects of the resin distribution mesh(B). After calculated under the same boundary conditions, the volume fractions of resin of two structure in the fluid domain were exhibited as Figure 6.

Figure 6: Volume fraction of resin of two structure in the fluid domain. (A: with extra resin distribution mesh; B: without extra resin distribution mesh)

As could be seen in Figure 6, the defects of dry spots under omega flow line seemed much serious after simply removing the extra distribution mesh. And because of the grooves in the caul plate, the resin came from the plates striped perpendicular to the omega flow line.

3.3 The effect of the permeability of the release fabrics and porous membranes

The release fabrics and porous membranes adopted in the tooling structures were used to sperate the auxiliary materials and the part. As with the studies of the permeabilities of release materials, dry spots near the inlet could not be eliminated by easily removing the extra distribution meshes.

The permeability of the release materials adopted above was about 10^{-12} m^2 , which is smaller than fiber preforms because the porosity of the release fabrics and porous membranes was quite low. Three other release materials with different permeabilities were also studied to search if the alteration of release materials might improve the impregnation conditions, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: The Volume fraction of resin in the structure with release materials of different permeabilities. (A: 10^{-11} m^2 ; B: 10^{-12} m^2 ; C: 10^{-13} m^2 ; D: 10^{-14} m^2)

Compared to Figure 7 (B), the gaps resulted from the groove channels in the caul plates would be more severe when the release materials with a higher permeability was used. And using the materials with lower permeability could improve the defects around the omega flow line. Particularly, adopting the release fabrics and porous membranes with permeability of about 10^{-14} m^2 could manufacture a defect-free part. The higher permeability might be helpful to accelerate the resin infusion, but it was harmful to improve the qualities of final parts.

The identical simulations were conducted without removing the resin distribution mesh (B), as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: The Volume fraction of resin in the structure before removing the resin distribution mesh (B) with release materials of different permeabilities. (A: 10^{-11} m^2 ; B: 10^{-12} m^2 ; C: 10^{-13} m^2 ; D: 10^{-14} m^2)

Compared to the result in 7 (D), the dry spot near the inlet was still existed in Figure 8 (D), suggesting that simply alter the release materials could not eliminate the defects without removing the extra resin distribution mesh.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a 3-D flow field of typical VARI process was established with the omega flow line, resin distribution mesh, caul plate, porous membrane, peel ply and preform to study the multi-dimensional multi-phase flow phenomenon near the inlet. The resin system in the fluid field was treated as a mixture with three phases: resin, air trapped in resin and residual air in the zone.

The extra resin distribution mesh between the omega flow line and caul plate was proved to result in the negative effect on the entirely infiltration of resin near the inlet. Using the materials with lower permeability could improve the defects around the omega flow line. The higher permeability of the release fabrics and porous membranes might be helpful to accelerate the resin infusion, but it was harmful to the qualities of final parts. Using the release materials with lower permeability and deserting the irrational resin distribution mesh simultaneously could lead to the defect-free parts.

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